

Local Government in Australia

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

Carol Mills

Institute for Public Policy and Governance
University of Technology Sydney

Partners

Eurac Research
Institute for Comparative Federalism
Italy

LMU Munich
Research Center for Public Procurement
Law and Administrative Cooperations
Germany

Autonomous University of Madrid
Institute of Local Law
Spain

Institut für Föderalismus
Institut du Fédéralisme
Institute of Federalism

University of Fribourg
Institute of Federalism
Switzerland

NALAS
Network of Associations of Local
Authorities of South East Europe
France

Ximpulse GmbH
Switzerland

KDZ
Center for Public Administration Research
Austria

Council of Europe
Congress of Local and Regional Authorities
France

Faculty of Political Science
and International Studies
University of Warsaw
University of Warsaw
Institute of Political Science
Poland

ZELS
Association of the Units of Local Self-Government
North Macedonia

University of the Western Cape
Dullah Omar Institute for Constitutional
Law, Governance and Human Rights
South Africa

Addis Ababa University
Center for Federalism and Governance Studies
Ethiopia

UNIVERSIDAD
NACIONAL DE
SAN MARTÍN

Universidad Nacional de General San Martín
School of Politics and Government
Argentina

SALGA
South African Local Government Association
South Africa

जवाहरलाल नेहरू विश्वविद्यालय
Jawaharlal Nehru University
Jawaharlal Nehru University
India

University of Technology Sydney
Institute for Public Policy and Governance
Centre for Local Government
Australia

National University of Singapore
Centre for Asian Legal Studies
Asia Pacific Centre for Environmental Law
Singapore

University of Western Ontario
Centre for Urban Policy and Local Governance
Canada

November 2021

The Country Report on Local Government in Australia is a product of the LoGov-project: “Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay”.

The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

LICENSE

CC BY 4.0

INFORMATION

Eurac Research
Viale Druso/Drususallee, 1
39100 Bolzano/Bozen – Italy

logov@eurac.edu
www.logov-rise.eu

SCIENTIFIC COORDINATION

Eurac Research: Karl Kössler

WP 1 – Local Responsibilities and Public Services

LMU Munich: Martin Burgi

WP 2 – Local Financial Arrangements

Universidad Autónoma de Madrid: Francisco Velasco Caballero

WP 3 – Structure of Local Government

University of Fribourg: Eva Maria Belser

WP 4 – Intergovernmental Relations of Local Government

NALAS – Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South East Europe: Elton Stafa

WP 5 – People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making

Ximpulse GmbH: Erika Schläppi

EDITORIAL TEAM

University of Technology Sydney: Carol Mills
Eurac Research: Karl Kössler, Theresia Morandell, Caterina Salvo, Annika Kress, Petra Malferttheiner

GRAPHIC DESIGN

Eurac Research: Alessandra Stefanut

COVER PHOTO

Jamie Davies/Unsplash

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 823961.

Contents

1. The System of Local Government in Australia.....	1
2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in Australia: An Introduction	6
2.2. <i>Provision of Services in Regional and Rural Areas</i>	8
3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in Australia: An Introduction	11
3.2. <i>Limiting Rate Increases in New South Wales and Victoria</i>	13
4.1. The Structure of Local Government in Australia: An Introduction	16
4.2. <i>Amalgamations in New South Wales</i>	18
5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Australia: An Introduction.....	21
5.2. <i>Changes in the Structure of Intergovernmental Relations and their Implications for Local Government</i>	23
6.1. People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making in Australia: An Introduction	26
6.2. <i>Innovative Approaches to Citizen Participation</i>	28

Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments

5.2. Changes in the Structure of Intergovernmental Relations and their Implications for Local Government

Carol Mills, *Institute for Public Policy and Governance, University of Technology Sydney*

Relevance of the Practice

It is not clear how changes in the structure of intergovernmental relations within the Australian Federation will affect the status of local governments. The ability of the sector through its peak body, the Australian Local Government Association (ALGA), to have its voice heard in policy debates and negotiations at a federal level has been severely curtailed. The implications of this exclusion not only in policy making but delivery of essential services and partnership in political leadership, may be examined as we evaluate the efficacy of our responses to Covid-19 pandemic.

Description of the Practice

The shift from the Council of Australian Governments (COAG) to a National Cabinet structure has excluded local government from the primary intergovernmental mechanism within Australia. More work needs to be done to understand the repercussions and implications of this shift. A review of the relative strengths and failings of the COAG model, the opportunities and limitation of the National Cabinet structure, capabilities and limits of current local governments' engagement and influence in the national arena and exploration of comparative practice and models in other countries.

Assessment of the Practice

While some lobbying has taken place by ALGA and some of the state level peak bodies for the inclusion of local government within National Cabinet, debate on this issue continues to be relatively muted. It is unclear whether the presence of local government within this intergovernmental mechanism would indeed make a significant difference to the sector or to the federation as a whole.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Local Government NSW, 'Local Government Representation at the National Cabinet Table' (2020) <<https://lgsw.org.au/Public/Policy/Campaigns-and-Initiatives/National-Cabinet-Representation/Public/Advocacy/national-cabinet-campaign.aspx?hkey=2496994f-f4c4-4804-8118-dedf515a7737>>

Sansom G, 'Does National Cabinet Really Matter? Positioning Local Government in Australia's Post-Covid Federation' (LGIU 2020) <<https://lgiu.org/briefing/does-national-cabinet-really-matter-positioning-local-government-in-australias-post-covid-federationin-this-opinion-piece-graham-sansom-a-former-ceo-of-the-australian-local-government-assoc/>>

Contacts

Local Government and the Changing
Urban-Rural Interplay
www.logov-rise.eu
logov@eurac.edu

This project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020 re-
search and innovation programme under
grant agreement No 823961.

